

Supplemental Table 7. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between marital status and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Marital status categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG increased if not married; odds of insufficient GWG increased if not married		Married Other	No	S
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents <18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337		NS association between marital status and GWG (compared adolescents gaining <20 lbs to those gaining 20+ lbs)	Single, divorced, or separated Married or cohabitation	Yes	NS
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥20 years of age	11 561	Unmarried women had higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) when compared to married women	NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) for unmarried women when compared to married women	Married Unmarried	No	S & NS
Bogaerts, A.	2012	Belgium	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in Flanders in 2009	54 022	Single status (vs. living with partner) had higher odds of excessive GWG		Single Cohabiting	No	S
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to marital status (single/divorced/separated/widowed vs married) or if living with spouse/partner (yes/no)	Single, divorced, separated, or widowed Married	Yes	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293		Marital status (single/divorced/separated/widowed vs married) or living with partner/spouse not associated with adequacy of GWG	Single, divorced, separated, or widowed Married	Yes	NS
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Higher risk of excessive GWG in Asians who are unmarried	NS difference in risk of insufficient GWG if unmarried	Married Unmarried	No	S & NS

Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy based on marital status (married vs unmarried)		Married Unmarried	Yes	S
Cunningham, S.D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women age 14-21 yrs old enrolled in the CenteringPregnancy Plus RCT (a multi-site prenatal care intervention) from 2008-2012; hospitals chosen for the RCT primarily served women who have low income and women from minority groups	505		Women having adequate vs excessive GWG did not differ by marital status (married/living with partner vs other)	Married or living with partner Other	Yes	NS
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	<u>Underweight</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if unmarried <u>Obese</u> : higher odds of excessive GWG if unmarried	Marital status NS on GWG adequacy for all groups except underweight (higher odds of insufficient GWG if unmarried) and obese (higher odds of excessive GWG if unmarried)	Married Unmarried	No	S & NS
Haile, Z. T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the population-based Infant Feeding Practices Study II from 2005-07	2 053	Significant differences in GWG adequacy by marital status (never married, married, other)		Never married Married Other	No	S
Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300	Significant differences in GWG adequacy according to marital status (married or unmarried)		Married Unmarried	No	S
Hickey, C. A.	1997a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income, multiparous Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806		NS association between insufficient GWG and marital status	Married or partnered Separated or divorced Single or no partner	Yes	NS
Hickey, C. A.	1992b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG evaluated as a percent of standard W/H (Rosso, 1985)	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women enrolled in prenatal care at two university-operated clinics	150		NS association between low GWG and marital status	Married Unmarried	Yes	NS

Khanolkar, A. R.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical record/birth certificate; IOM 2009	All women who gave birth in Washington State from 2006-08	181 948	Significant difference in adequacy of GWG according to marital status (married vs single/unknown)		Married Single/unknown	No	S
Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if not married/not living with partner	NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG for married/cohabitating vs unmarried/not cohabitating women	Married or cohabitating Not married or not cohabitating	No	S & NS
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619	Higher odds of excessive GWG if married (vs not married)		Married Unmarried	No	S
Loris, P.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; Morse et al. 1975 (standard GWG curve)	Adolescents age 13-19 years in the Sacramento area who attended adolescent-specific pregnancy clinics or programs from 1979 -82	145		NS difference in total GWG based on marital status (married vs not married)	Married Unmarried	Yes	NS
Nunnery, D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women attending a WIC clinic (for low-income women) in 2014 who were receiving WIC as a maternity client and were ≥18 years old	160		In multivariate regression: NS association between marital status (single/divorced/separated vs married/living together) and odds of excessive GWG	Single, divorced, or separated Married or living together	Yes	NS
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Decreased odds of insufficient GWG if single/separated (vs married/living with partner); decreased odds of excessive GWG if single/separated (vs married/living with partner)		Married or cohabitating Single or separated	No	S
Ratan, B. M.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Low-income women with obesity who enrolled in prenatal care at a specific clinic in Houston, Texas from September 2013 August 2017; all women were receiving social assistance (CHIP Perinate or Medicaid)	772		NS effect of relationship to father of infant on odds of excessive or insufficient GWG (married, partner, involved, not involved)	Measured as 'relationship to father of the infant': Spouse Significant other Involved Not involved Other	Yes	NS

Rosal, M. C.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study involving Non-Latina White and Latina women	571		No association between marital status and general adequacy of GWG (looked at prevalence of 3 different GWG adequacy categories by whether women were divorced, married, or single)	Divorced Married Single	No	NS
Sangi-Haghpeykar, H.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Hispanic women who delivered at a specific hospital in Texas	282	Higher odds of excessive GWG if unmarried (vs married)		Married Unmarried	Yes	S
Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: positive association with being divorced (vs being married)	NS association between total GWG (for all women) and being single (vs married) NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG (for women in all BMI categories) by marital status	Married Single Divorced	Yes	S & NS
Stogianni, A.	2019	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guidelines identified	Women with and without diabetes who were admitted to a specific hospital in Kronoberg from January 2009 - December 2012	280		Among women with diabetes or without diabetes, marital status was not significantly associated with high GWG (GWG \geq 8 kg)	Married or living with partner Living alone	No	NS
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were \geq 18 years old	250 857	Increased odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if unmarried (vs married); increased odds of excessive GWG if married		Married Unmarried	No	S
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were \geq 18 years old	1 988		NS effect of marital status (married vs not) on general adequacy of GWG (looked at distribution of women in insufficient, adequate and excessive categories)	Married Unmarried	Yes	NS
Wright, C.	2013	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Low-income urban women enrolled in a community-based participatory research study; all women attended a social service and advocacy agency for low-income women	101		NS difference in GWG category (adequate vs excessive) by marital status (married/living with partner, single); analyses only compared GWG adequacy between women with the same characteristic, e.g., compared proportion of White women with adequate vs excessive GWG	Married or living with partner Single	Yes	NS